

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial activity of novel Pd(II) complexes with anthracenyl-based Schiff bases

Ana Kandić,^{a, 0009-0002-4709-5628} Tamara Petrović,^{b, 0000-0003-1818-8710} Marija Tanović,^{c, 0000-0002-4363-7824} Jovana Anđelković,^{d, 0009-0009-5786-3185} Marija Dimitrijević,^{e, 0000-0003-1816-0400} Stefan Nikolić,^{a, 0000-0002-0164-134X} Tatjana Mihajilov-Krstev,^{d, 0000-0002-7642-5879} Sanja Grgurić-Šipka,^{b, 0000-0003-1906-535X} Jelena Poljarević^{*b, 0000-0002-6706-0281}

^a Innovative centre, Faculty of Chemistry, Studentski trg 12-16, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

^b University of Belgrade - Faculty of Chemistry, Department for General and Inorganic Chemistry, Studentski trg 12-16, 11 000 Belgrade

^c University of Belgrade - Institute for Multidisciplinary Research, Kneza Višeslava 1, 11030 Beograd

^d Department of Biology and Ecology, Faculty of Sciences and Mathematics, University of Niš, Višegradska 33, 18000 Niš, Serbia

^e Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Medicine, University of Niš, Blvd. Dr Zorana Đinđića 81, 18000 Niš, Serbia

*Corresponding author: jelenal@chem.bg.ac.rs

Abstract

Four new Schiff bases, one well-known Schiff base, and five new Pd(II) complexes were synthesized, characterized, and evaluated in their antimicrobial activities. New ligands were synthesized in the reaction of 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde and phenylenediamines (4-methyl-1,2-phenylenediamine, 4-chloro-1,2-phenylenediamine, 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-phenylenediamine, and methyl 3,4-diaminobenzoate). The chemical structures of all synthesized compounds were confirmed using standard NMR and IR spectroscopy, and MS spectrometry, as well as molar conductivity measurements, while their purity was evaluated by elemental analysis. The antimicrobial activities of these novel compounds were assessed *in vitro* against a representative panel of microbial strains. The test organisms included three Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*), four Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, and *Enterobacter aerogenes*), and a single yeast strain (*Candida albicans* ATCC 10231), selected to assess antifungal activity. The assay included two commercial antibiotics, streptomycin and chloramphenicol, as positive controls to ensure assay validity and enable comparative analysis of antimicrobial activity. The free ligands exhibited limited antimicrobial activity, while the metal complexes demonstrated significantly enhanced, broader-spectrum activity. Complex **C2** (with N,N'-(4-methyl-1,2-phenylene)bis(1-(anthracen-9-yl)methanimine)) showed the best activity, surpassing the standard antibiotics streptomycin and chloramphenicol in several cases.

Keywords: palladium complex, 9-anthracenyl aldehyde, Schiff base, antimicrobial activity

1. Introduction

Microorganisms are present in the water, soil, air, and in the human body. While many play beneficial roles, a significant number are pathogenic and responsible for various diseases. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 13.7 million deaths in 2019 were associated with infectious agents. Alarmingly, projections estimate that bacterial infections could cause up to 10 million deaths annually by 2050 [1,2]. During the twentieth century, antibiotic development experienced golden decades (1940-1962), but ultimately ended with a decade marked by the rise of pathogens' resistance to antimicrobials [3,4]. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is reflected in microorganisms' expression of enzymes that can degrade, modify, or inactivate antimicrobials, or by modifying the antibiotic's targets (e.g., DNA replication or the protein translational process), thereby changing the cell or cell wall composition [5]. Therefore, scientists worldwide are working on developing new, efficient antimicrobials, and metals and metal compounds represent significant sources for this purpose. [6]. The Community for Open Antimicrobial

Drug Discovery (CO-ADD) database contains over 1000 metal-based structures, comprising 29 metal ions (transition metals, lanthanides, and main group elements)[7]. An analysis of the data that Frei *et al.* previously reported that palladium complexes rank among the top three of the sixteen tested compound groups in terms of biological activity. Particularly, palladium-based compounds constitute 14% of the active and non-toxic agents, placing them second only to platinum complexes (18%) [8]. The antimicrobial activity of metal complexes depends on several factors, including the chelate effect (complexes with bidentate or polydentate ligands generally exhibit greater activity than those with monodentate ligands), the nature of the ligands, the overall charge of the complex (cationic > neutral > anionic), the type of counter ion, and the nuclearity (binuclear > mononuclear) [9]. Since both Pd(II) and Pt(II) are soft Lewis's acids, they prefer to form stronger bonds with nitrogen or sulfur donors (soft bases) than oxygen donors (hard bases). [10]. Concerning antimicrobial activity, the latest literature data indicate that their antimicrobial properties have good prospects. Commonly used ligands in such compounds were N[^]O, N[^]N or N[^]S type, and a few of the palladium compounds are even cyclometalated with N[^]C ligands. Additionally, Pd(II) complexes with cyclic tetradentate N-ligands expressed significant antimicrobial activity as potential agents for photodynamic therapy, even better than the well-known ampicillin and nystatin drugs [8].

Among organic compounds, imines, also known as azomethines or Schiff bases, have applications in industry (food, dye, fungicidal, agrochemical), as well as in analytical, supramolecular chemistry, catalysis, material science, separation and encapsulation processes, biomedical applications, and the formation of compounds. Schiff bases belong to a sub-group of imines, also known as azomethines. Their remarkable popularity in organic chemistry arises from their facile synthesis using inexpensive starting materials and their notable air stability. Each novel Schiff base derivative has attracted significant attention due to the presence of the imine (-C=N) bond, which constitutes the core of these molecules and plays a crucial role in their antimicrobial activity [11,12]. The azomethine nitrogen serves as a key coordination site for metal ions, and metal complexes containing Schiff bases exhibit a wide range of biological activities-[13]. The enhanced biological activity of their metal complexes is believed to arise not only from structural factors but also from properties such as solubility, dipole moment, cell permeability [14], and potential enzymatic interactions. The Schiff base with lipophilic groups and its metal complexes express higher toxicity on bacterial strains. The lipophilicity of complexes is enhanced due to delocalization of π -electrons in the chelate ring, which subsequently favors their permeation through the lipid layer of the cell membrane. Also, Schiff bases are excellent chelate ligands, and their corresponding metal complexes are very thermodynamically stable [15,16,17]. Schiff-base palladium(II) complexes exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities, functioning as antiprotozoal [18], antibacterial [19,20], antifungal [20], antitumor [21,22], and antiviral [22] agents. Furthermore, palladium(II) complexes containing only nitrogen-donor ligands have also exhibited antimicrobial activity [23].

Over the past decade, numerous studies have demonstrated that palladium(II) complexes containing Schiff bases exhibit notable antibacterial activity. Pui *et al.* reported palladium(II) complexes coordinated with salicylaldehyde-derived Schiff bases and amino acids, which showed activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Complexes containing alanine and glycine exhibited enhanced lipophilicity due to free hydroxyl groups and significantly higher antibacterial activity compared to palladium chloride. [24]

A 2016 comparative study of palladium(II) and nickel(II) complexes with N[^]O Schiff bases revealed superior antibacterial and antifungal activity for palladium(II), particularly against *P. desmolyticum* and *S. aureus*. [25] Similarly, palladium(II) complexes derived from o-vanillin and benzylamine-based N[^]O Schiff bases showed greater antibacterial potency than the free ligands, especially toward *P. aeruginosa* and *S. sonnei*. [26]

In recent years, several reports have focused on Schiff bases forming bi-, tri-, or tetradentate coordination with palladium(II). [27,28,29] Bidentate palladium(II) complexes with N[^]C-type Schiff bases exhibited the most promising activity [28], while tridentate palladium(II) complexes coordinated via pyrrole nitrogen, imine nitrogen, and amino acid oxygen atoms also displayed antibacterial activity, whereas the free ligands were inactive. [27] Moreover, a tetracoordinated palladium(II) complex with 5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzaldehyde- β -alanine demonstrated rapid fungicidal and bactericidal effects. [29]

Recent studies have demonstrated that Schiff bases derived from 9-anthraldehyde and primary amines, as well as their complexes with rare-earth metals and ruthenium, exhibit promising antibacterial activity. [30,31] Complexes of Er(III), Pr(III), and Yb(III) coordinated to an N[^]N-type Schiff base (pyridine-3,4-diamine/9-anthraldehyde, 1:2) displayed

low MIC values against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*, with the Pr(III) complex being the most active [30]. In addition, a ruthenium(II) complex containing an anthracene-based Schiff base showed pronounced activity against Gram-positive *B. subtilis* (MIC = 3.11 ± 0.23 μM), surpassing ampicillin. [31]

Based on the literature data we have presented in this study, synthesis and chemical characterization of anthracenyl-based Schiff bases and their corresponding Pd(II) complexes followed by evaluation of their in vitro antimicrobial potential against a representative panel of microbial strains: three Gram-positive bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*), four Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, and *Enterobacter aerogenes*), and a single yeast strain (*Candida albicans* ATCC 10231), selected to assess antifungal activity.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials and methods

[K₂PdCl₄] (**CP**) was prepared according to the literature procedure [32]. Ligands **L1** have been previously reported in the literature [33], while **L2-L5** are new and were synthesized according to a slightly modified procedure for **L1**. Aromatic diamines (1,2-phenylenediamine, 4-methyl-1,2-phenylenediamine, 4-chloro-1,2-phenylenediamine, 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-phenylenediamine, methyl 3,4-diaminobenzoate) and 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde used for ligand synthesis were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. Solvents were obtained and used without further purification. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Nicolet 6700 FTIR spectrometer using the ATR technique. ¹H

and ¹³C spectra were acquired on a Varian instrument (Agilent, USA) with a 5 mm ATB probe, using standard pulse sequences, at 400 MHz for ¹H and 100.52 MHz for ¹³C nuclei. Chemical shifts for ¹H and ¹³C were referenced to residual ¹H and ¹³C present in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-d₆), chloroform (CDCl₃), and acetone ((CD₃)₂CO). Elemental analyses were performed at the ElementarVarioMicroTube CHN analyser. Molar conductivities of 1 mM complex solutions were recorded using the Crison Multimeter MM 41 instrument. Mass spectra were recorded on the Mass spectrometer Orbitrap Exploris 240 with UliMate 3000 RSLC nano system (MS240 / 250A) using CH₃CN as solvent in positive mode.

2.2. Antimicrobial assay

2.2.1. Microbial strains

The *in vitro* antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds was assessed against a well-defined panel of reference microbial strains encompassing both Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, ATCC 25923, *Bacillus cereus*, ATCC 11778, and *Enterococcus faecalis* ATCC 29212) and Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, ATCC 29212, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, ATCC 9027, *Salmonella enteritidis*, ATCC 13076, and *Enterobacter aerogenes*, ATCC 13048), as well as a pathogenic yeast species (*Candida albicans* ATCC 10231).

2.2.2 Microwell dilution method

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of the test compounds were determined using the broth microdilution method as outlined by the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI, 2012 [34]).

Bacterial suspensions were prepared from overnight cultures in sterile 0.9% NaCl and adjusted to a turbidity equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standard (approximately 10⁸ CFU/mL). Stock solutions of the compounds **L1-L5**, **C1-C5**, and **CP** were prepared in 6% (v/v) aqueous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at a concentration of 310 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The bacterial inoculum was added to all 96-well microtiter plates containing the compounds at the appropriate concentrations, and the plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Each well had a final volume of 100 μL , containing bacterial suspensions at a concentration of 10⁶ CFU/mL. Streptomycin and chloramphenicol served as positive controls, while

DMSO was used as a negative control. Bacterial growth was visualized by adding 20 μl of 0.5% (w/w) triphenyltetrazolium chloride (TTC) aqueous solution [35]. Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) was defined as the lowest concentration of the compounds **L1-L5**, **C1-C5**, and **CP** that inhibited visible growth (red colored pellet on the bottom of the wells after the addition of TTC), while minimal bactericidal concentration (MBC) was defined as the lowest concentration of the compound that killed 99.9% of bacterial cells. To determine the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), aliquots from wells showing no visible bacterial growth were subcultured onto Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA) and incubated at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours.

2.3. Synthesis

2.3.1. Synthesis of ligands

L1 (*N,N'*-(1,2-phenylene)*bis*(1-(anthracen-9-yl)methanimine), **L2** (*N,N'*-(4-methyl-1,2-phenylene)*bis*(1-(anthracen-9-yl)methanimine), **L3** (methyl-3,4-*bis*(anthracene-9-methylene)aminobenzoate, **L4** (*N,N'*-(4-chloro-1,2-phenylene)-*bis*(1-(anthracen-9-yl)methanimine), and **L5** (*N,N'*-(4,5-dimethyl-1,2-phenylene)-*bis*(1-(anthracen-9-yl)methanimine), were synthesized according to slightly modified literature procedure [33]. 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde and corresponding diamine were mixed in a 2:1 molar ratio using ethanol as solvent (Scheme 1). Ligand **L1** have been reported previously [33], while **L2-L5** are new.

Scheme 1 Reaction scheme for **L1-L5** synthesis

L1: 1.5260 g (7.20 mmol) of 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde dissolved in 10 mL of ethanol, and 0.4000 g (3.70 mmol) of 1,2-phenylenediamine in 10 mL of ethanol was added dropwise. The resulting solution was left overnight at room temperature under constant stirring. After that time, the orange precipitate was filtered and dried in vacuo. Yield: 63.39% (1.13 g). Chemical characterization data are in accordance with literature data [33].

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1578 and 1610 (ar C-C), 1623 (C=N st), 3050 (C-H st).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.09-7.13 (t, 4H, **C3**, **C4**, **C5**, **C6**), 7.36-7.39 and 7.43-7.50 (m, 8H, **C15**, **C16**, **C10**, **C11**, **C15'**, **C16'**, **C10'**, **C11'**), 7.96-7.98 (d, 4H, **C17**, **C9**, **C17'**, **C9'**), 8.50 (s, 2H, **C13**, **C13'**), 8.84-8.86 (d, 4H, **C12**, **C14**, **C12'**, **C14'**), 9.81 (s, 2H, **C7**, **C7'**).

^{13}C NMR (100.52 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 120.97 (**C1**, **C2**, **C4**, **C5**), 125.11 (**C3**, **C6**), 125.25 (**C13**, **C13'**), 126.66-131.19 (C atoms from anthracene rings), 145.45 (**C19**, **C21**, **C19'**, **C21'**), 161.57 (**C7**).

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode (calculated for M (C₃₆H₂₄N₂ = 484.19 [M+H]⁺ = 485.20)), found [M+H]⁺ = 485.20

L2: In a round-bottom flask, 0.9920 g (4.70 mmol) of 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde was dissolved in 15 mL of acetonitrile. A solution of 0.2604 g (2.13 mmol) of 4-methyl-1,2-phenylenediamine in 20 mL of ethanol was then added dropwise to the reaction mixture under continuous stirring. The mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The following day, the reaction mixture was filtered, and the resulting orange precipitate was left to dry in a desiccator. Yield: 51.23% (0.54 g).

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1589 and 1622 (ar C-C), 1661 (C=N st), 3046 (ar C-H st).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-d₆) δ (ppm): 2.53 (s, 3H, CH₃), 7.12 (t, 2H, C3, C5, C6), 7.41-7.74 (m, 8H, C15, C16, C10, C11, C15', C16', C10', C11'), 8.05-8.21 (m, 4H, C17, C9, C17', C9'), 8.65-9.08 (m, 6H, C13, C13', C12, C14, C12', C14'), 9.84 (s, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 21.35 (CH₃), 123.52-130.65 (anthracene rings, C1-C6).

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode (calculated for M (C₃₇H₂₆N₂ = 498.21, [M+H]⁺ = 499.22)), found [M+H]⁺ = 499.21

L3: 0.9960 g (4.70 mmol) of 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde was dissolved in 20 mL of ethanol, and 0.4006 g (2.40 mmol) of 4-methyl-3,4-diaminobenzoate in 20 mL of ethanol was added dropwise with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux (80 °C) overnight. The resulting orange precipitate was collected by filtration and dried in a desiccator. Yield: 55.84% (0.73 g).

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1337 (C-O-C st as), 1537 (ar C-C), 1622 (C=N st), 1714 (C=O st), 3052, 2949 (C-H st).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 3.80 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 5.96 (s, 3H, C3, C10, C10'), 6.83 (d, 2H, C11, C11'), 7.61 (m, 6H, C15, C15', C16, C16', C17, C17'), 7.70 (dd, 2H, C9, C9'), 7.86 (d, 1H, C5), 8.18 (d, 3H, C6, C12, C12'), 8.78 (t, 4H, C13, C13', C14, C14'), 9.85 (s, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, DMSO) δ (ppm): 52.18 (-OCH₃), 123.56-134.63 (C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C atoms from anthracene ring), 166.97 (C=O).

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode (calculated for M (C₃₈H₂₆N₂O₂ = 542.20, [M+H]⁺ = 543.21)), found [M+H]⁺ = 543.20

L4: 1.1120 g (5.43 mmol) of 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde was dissolved in 20 mL of ethanol, and 0.3870 g (2.71 mmol) of 4-chloro-1,2-phenylenediamine in 20 mL of ethanol was added dropwise to the flask. The reaction mixture was left stirring overnight at room temperature. The next day, the solution was filtered, and the resulting orange precipitate was left to dry in a desiccator. Yield: 64.07% (0.72 g).

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 731 (C-Cl), 1520 (ar C-C), 1624 (C=N st), 3050 (ar C-H st).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 7.11 (m, 3H, C3, C5, C6), 7.41-7.70 (m, 8H, C15, C16, C10, C11, C15', C16', C10', C11'), 8.07-8.10 (t, 4H, C9, C17, C9', C17'), 8.85-8.71 (m, 6H, C12, C13, C14, C12', C13', C14'), 9.80 (d, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 123.68-134.86 (C1, C3, C4, C5, C6, C atoms from anthracene rings), 159.92 (C2, C7, C7').

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode (calculated for M (C₃₆H₂₃N₂Cl = 518.15, [M+H]⁺ = 519.16)), found [M+H]⁺ = 519.16

L5: 1.5560 g (7.54 mmol) 9-anthracenecarboxaldehyde was dissolved in 20 mL of ethanol, and a solution of 0.5413 g (3.77 mmol) of 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-phenyldiamine in 20 mL of ethanol was added dropwise to the flask. The reaction mixture was left stirring overnight at room temperature. The next day, the solution was filtered, and the resulting orange precipitate was left to dry in a desiccator. Yield: 65.61% (1.25 g).

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 1443 (CH₃ δ as; CH₃-Car), 1519 (ar C-H), 1623 (C=N st), 3048 (ar C-H st).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 2.42 (s, 6H, **CH**₃), 7.09 (t, 4H, **C3**, **C6**, **C10**, **C10'**), 7.43 (dd, 6H, **C15**, **C16**, **C11**, **C15'**, **C16'**, **C11'**), 8.10 (d, 4H, **C17**, **C9**, **C17'**, **C9'**), 8.73 (s, 2H, **13**, **13'**), 8.80 (d, 4H, **C12**, **C14**, **C12'**, **C14'**), 9.75 (s, 2H, **C7**, **C7'**).

^{13}C NMR (100.52 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ (ppm): 51.41 (**CH**₃), 113.57-148.29 (**C3**, **C6**, **C** atoms from anthracene ring), 157.86 (**C5**, **C4**), 166.80 (**C1**, **C2**, **C7**, **C7'**).

HESI-MS (m/z), CH_3CN : positive mode (calculated for M ($\text{C}_{38}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2$) = 512.23, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ = 513.23), found $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ = 513.23

2.3.2. Synthesis of complexes

Starting palladium(II) complex, $[\text{K}_2\text{PdCl}_4]$, was dissolved in water, and a solution of 1.2 equivalents of the corresponding ligand was added dropwise. Ligands were dissolved in methanol (**L1**, **L2**), or ethanol (**L3**, **L4**, **L5**). The resulting mixture was left on reflux for 4h (**C2**, **C4**, **C5**), or at room temperature overnight (**C1**, **C3**) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2 Reaction scheme for **C1-C5** synthesis.

C1: In a solution of 0.0677 g (0.14 mmol) **L1** in 10 mL of methanol, a solution of 0.0400 g (0.12 mmol) $\text{K}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ in 10 mL of water was added dropwise. The resulting mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. The next day, the solution was filtered, and the filtrate was placed in the refrigerator to allow crystallization of the product. After three days, a red precipitate formed. Yield: 55.12% (0.04 g).

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 422 (**Pd-N st**), 1522-1623 (**arC-C**), 1666 (**C=N st**), 3050 (**ar C-H st**).

^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 7.56 and 7.69 (dt, 12H, **C3**, **C4**, **C5**, **C6**, **C15**, **C16**, **C10**, **C11**, **C15'**, **C16'**, **C10'**, **C11'**), 8.07 (d, 4H, **C17**, **C9**, **C17'**, **C9'**), 8.71 (s, 2H, **C13**, **C13'**), 8.99 (d, 4H, **C12**, **C14**, **C12'**, **C14'**), 11.54 (s, 2H, **C7**, **C7'**).

^{13}C NMR (100.52 MHz, CDCl_3) δ (ppm): 123.52-132.12 (**C1**, **C2**, **C4**, **C5**, **C3**, **C6**, **C13**, **C13'**, **C** atoms from anthracene rings), 135.24 (**C19**, **C21**, **C19'**, **C21'**), 193.01 (**C7**).

HESI-MS (m/z), CH_3CN : (calculated for M ($\text{PdCl}_2\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2$) = 660.04, $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{H}]^+$ = 589.09, $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{H}+\text{CH}_3\text{CN}]^+$ = 630.12), found $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{H}]^+$ = 589.09, $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{H}+\text{CH}_3\text{CN}]^+$ = 630.12

Anal. Calculated for $\text{PdCl}_2\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2$ (%): N-4.23; C- 65.32; H-3.63; found (%) N-3.85; C-65.68; H-3.93.

C2: In a solution of 0.0261 g (0.05 mmol) of **L2** in 5 mL of methanol, a solution of 0.0500 g (0.15 mmol) $\text{K}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ in 3 mL of methanol was added. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 4 hours at 65 °C. The resulting red precipitate was isolated by filtration and left to dry in a desiccator. Yield: 77% (0.08 g).

IR (ATR) $\nu_{\text{max}}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 455 (**Pd-N st**), 1528 and 1600 (**arC-C**), 1616 (**C=N st**), 3091 (**ar C-H st**).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 2.37 (d, 3H, CH₃), 6.18-6.26 (d, 3H, C3, C5, C6), 7.18-7.35 (m, 2H, C10, C10', C11, C11'), 7.64-8.55 (m, 12H, C15, C16, C15', C16', C17, C9, C17', C9', C12, C14, C12', C14'), 8.93-9.00 (m, 2H, C13, C13'), 10.00 (d, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 21.05 (C8), 119.51-147.60 (anthracene rings, C1-C6), 151.00 (C7, C7').

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode :(calculated for M (PdCl₂C₃₇H₂₆N₂= 674.05, [M-2Cl-H]⁺ = 603.11)), found [M-2Cl-H]⁺ = 603.10

Anal.Calculated for PdCl₂C₃₇H₂₆N₂ (%): N- 4.15; C- 65.75; H-3.85; found (%) N-4.35; C-65.38; H-3.53.

C3: In a solution of 0.0400 g (0.12 mmol) of K₂[PdCl₄] in 3 mL of water, a solution of 0.0500 g (0.09 mmol) of L3 in 5 mL of ethanol was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. A red precipitate was obtained which was isolated by filtration. Yield: 58.54% (0.04 g).

IR (ATR) ν_{max}/cm⁻¹: 447 (Pd-N st), 1264 and 1287 (C-O-C st), 1531 (ar C-C), 1599 (C=N st), 1721 (C=O st), 2952 (C-H st).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 3.90 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 6.57 (s, 3H, C3, C10, C10'), 7.37 (t, 2H, C11, C11'), 7.49 (d, 2H, C15, C15'), 7.66 (d, 2H, C16, C16'), 7.81 (t, 2H, C17, C17'), 7.94 (t, 3H, C5, C9, C9'), 8.25 (d, 2H, C12, C12'), 8.47 (d, 1H, C14), 8.51 (d, 1H, C14'), 8.98 (d, 2H, C13, C13'), 9.04 (s, 1H, C6), 10.01 (s, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, DMSO) δ (ppm): 52.52 (-OCH₃), 125.12 (C3), 129.05 (C6), 129.70 (C5), 141.76 -153.05 (C atoms from anthracene ring), 153.13 (C7), 165.63 (C=O).

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode :(calculated for M (PdCl₂C₃₈H₂₆N₂O₂= 718.04, [M-2Cl+H]⁺ = 649.11)), found [M-2Cl+H]⁺ = 649.11

Anal.Calculated for PdCl₂C₃₈H₂₆N₂O₂ (%): N- 3.89; C- 63.39; H-3.61; found (%) N-4.25; C-63.05; H-3.91.

C4: In a solution of 0.0400 g (0.12 mmol) K₂[PdCl₄] in 1mL of water, a solution of 0.0490 g (0.10 mmol) L4 in 4 mL of ethanol was added. This reaction mixture was refluxed and stirred for 4 hours at 80 °C. Upon completion, the resulting red precipitate was separated by vacuum filtration and dried in a desiccator. Yield: 52% (0.04g).

IR (ATR) ν_{max}/cm⁻¹: 458 (Pd-N st), 732 (C-Cl), 1527 (ar C-C), 1674 (C=N st), 3088 (ar C-H st).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 6.33-6.44 (d, 6H, C3, C6, C5), 7.36-7.95 (m, 8H, C17, C17', C9, C9', C10, C10', C11, C11'), 8.21 (m, 4H, C15, C16, C15', C16'), 8.49-8.53 (t, 2H, C13, C13'), 8.89-9.01 (m, 4H, C12, C14, C12', C14'), 9.94 (d, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 120.74-146.18 (C atoms from anthracene rings, C1-C6), 163.26 and 162.74 (C7, C7')

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode :(calculated for M (PdCl₃C₃₆H₂₃N₂= 694.00, [M-2Cl+H]⁺ = 625.07)), found [M-2Cl+H]⁺ = 625.05

Anal.Calculated for PdCl₃C₃₆H₂₃N₂ (%): N-4.02; C- 62.08; H-3.30; found (%) N-4.23; C-61.76; H-3.67.

C5: In a solution of 0.0400 g (0.12 mmol) K₂[PdCl₄] in 2 mL of water, a solution of 0.0450 g (0.10 mmol) L5 in 4 mL of ethanol was added. The resulting solution was refluxed and stirred for 4 hours at 80 °C. During heating, a color change from light orange to dark cherry indicates the progress of the reaction. The obtained precipitate was separated by filtration and left to dry in a desiccator. Yield: 40% (0.03 g).

IR (ATR) ν_{max}/cm⁻¹: 448 (Pd-N st), 1412 and 1431 (C-H st), 1478 -1666 (ar C-C), 1597 (C=N st), 3030 (ar C-H st).

¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 2.26-2.32 (d, 6H, CH₃), 6.14 (s, 3H, C3, C6), 7.13-7.92 (m, 8H, C10, C10', C11, C11', C15, C15', C16, C16'), 8.22-8.55 (m, 4H, C17, C9, C17', C9'), 8.55 (d, 2H, C13, C13'), 8.96-9.02 (m, 4H, C12, C14, C12', C14'), 9.97 (t, 2H, C7, C7').

¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ (ppm): 19.42 (CH₃, C13, C13'), 121.97-130.99 (C1, C2, C3, C4, C5, C6, C7, C7', C atoms from anthracene rings), 142.26 (C21, C21', C19, C19'), 161.17 (C20, C20', C18, C18').

HESI-MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode :(calculated for M (PdCl₂C₃₈H₂₈N₂= 688.07, [M-2Cl-H]⁺ = 617.12)), found [M-2Cl-H]⁺ = 617.12

Anal.Calculated for PdCl₂C₃₈H₂₈N₂ (%): N-4.06; C- 66.14; H-4.06; found (%) N-4.38; C-66.49; H-3.89.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 IR spectroscopy

The characteristic bands in the IR spectra of all ligands and complexes correspond to C=N standard, C-C aromatic, and C-H valence standard vibrations. Aromatic C-C valence vibrations for all complexes were observed from 1526-1600 cm^{-1} , while stretching C-H vibrations were observed around 3000-3100 cm^{-1} . The most important bands corresponding to C=N standard vibrations were observed for single ligands around 1660 cm^{-1} , whereas for the corresponding complexes, these bands were shifted to lower values around 1615 cm^{-1} .

In the IR spectrum of **C3**, the band at 1721 cm^{-1} is observed, which corresponds to C=O standard vibrations (Figure S1-S10).

3.2 NMR spectroscopy

In the ^1H NMR spectra of all synthesized ligands, characteristic bands of imine protons appear in the area of 8.70-10.00 ppm, and for the protons from aromatic rings, which appear in the area of 6.00-9.00 ppm. In the ^1H NMR spectra of complexes, these bands are shifted downfield (to higher values of chemical shifts). Those shifts are the consequence of electron density movement to the metal ion after the ligand coordination *via* imine N atoms. Characteristic bands for protons from methyl groups on aromatic rings in complexes **C2** and **C5** are placed at 2.40-2.60 ppm, while protons corresponding to the methyl group in **C3** were at 3.90 ppm due to the induction effect of the oxygen atom. For the newly synthesized **L2-L5**, the absence of amine and aldehyde group protons is proof of imine synthesis (Figure S11-S38). The most significant changes in ^1H NMR spectra of metal complexes compared to ligands are visible for the chemical shifts of imine protons (C7 and C7' atoms in the structure).

In the ^{13}C NMR spectra of complexes, signals for the imine carbon atoms are noticed at around 165 ppm. In this area, there is one more signal in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **C3** since in its structure carbonyl group is present. Signals for carbon atoms from methyl groups in complexes **C2** and **C5** are placed at around 20 ppm, while signals for carbon atoms from methyl groups in **C3** are noticed at around 55 ppm. Signals for aromatic carbon atoms are in the area from 120 to 150 ppm. The highest values in that area are for the carbon atoms directly bonded to oxygen (**C3**) or a chlorine atom (**C4**) (Figure S11-S38).

3.3. Mass spectrometry

All ligands and complexes were also characterized by Heated ESI-MS using positive ionization mode. In the mass spectra of all ligands, one type of peak, $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ ion is observed, corresponding to the following m/z values: 485.20 (**L1**), 499.21 (**L2**), 543.20 (**L3**), 519.16 (**L4**), and 513.23 (**L5**). High-intense peaks in all complexes were observed for: $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}-\text{H}]^+$ (**C1**, **C2**, **C5**), $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}+\text{H}]^+$ (**C3**), and $[\text{M}-2\text{Cl}]^+$ (**C4**) (Figures S39-48).

3.4. Molar conductivity

The molar conductivity values of the synthesized complexes are presented in Table 1. In general, these measurements provide insight into the nature of the complexes, indicating whether they are neutral (lowest values), cationic, or anionic. According to literature data, conductivity values vary for all three complex types depending on the solvent. The five Pd(II) complexes reported here were dissolved in DMSO at a concentration of 1 mM, and their measured molar conductivities are consistent with type "0" (neutral) complexes [36], which is proposed and confirmed by NMR and IR data.

Table 1. Values for the molar conductivity of **C1-C5**

complex	molar conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) in DMSO
C1	4.40
C2	16.00
C3	6.80
C4	3.07
C5	3.33

3.5. Antimicrobial activity

To treat bacterial infections, antibacterial medications have been used successfully; however, the main issue is the development of resistance in various organisms to antibiotics [37]. The synthesis of new compounds is a chance for a successful battle against various microbes. It was found that metal complexes have promising activity [7]. The results in Table 2 demonstrate the antimicrobial activity of Schiff bases, as well as the synergistic effect of Schiff bases and palladium(II) ion. The antimicrobial properties of the ligands (**L1-L5**) and their corresponding Pd(II) complexes (**C1-C5**) were assessed against a range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains, as well as the fungal strain *C. albicans*. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values revealed a significant improvement in activity for most metal complexes compared to their parent ligands, highlighting the role of metal coordination in increasing antimicrobial potency.

The free ligands (**L1-L5**) exhibited minimal antimicrobial activity against the majority of tested strains, with most MIC values exceeding 310 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. However, ligands **L4** through **L5** showed some activity against *B. cereus*, *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. enteritidis*, with MIC values ranging from 10 to 160 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. In addition, none of the ligands showed appreciable activity against *S. aureus* or *E. aerogenes*, suggesting a limited antibacterial spectrum in their uncoordinated forms. On the other hand, the metal complexes, the metal complexes (**C1-C5**) showed significantly enhanced antimicrobial activity. Complexes **C2** through **C5** showed strong and broad-spectrum antibacterial activity, with MIC values ranging from 1 to 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ against most strains, while for some strains the MIC value was higher, and ranged up to 80. **C2** complex showed remarkable potency across all tested bacterial species, including *E. coli* (2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), *S. enteritidis* (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and *P. aeruginosa* (5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), while also showing moderate antifungal activity against *C. albicans* (160 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$). Similarly, **C5** was effective against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, with MIC values in the range of 1 to 80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. According to chelation theory, the metal complexes exhibit greater activity than the free ligands. Due to the partial sharing of positive charge with the donor groups of the ligand, chelation reduces the polarity of the metals, and the lipophilic nature of the central ion increases as a consequence of the increase in the delocalization of π electrons over the whole chelate ring. This enhances the complex's lipophilic character and makes it easier to penetrate the cell membrane of microbes. Also, metal ions can produce reactive oxygen species, which disrupt microbial enzyme functions and thus improve the antimicrobial activity of the complex. [38].

In the study of *Arslan et al.*, it was revealed that complexes with different metals and N^N Schiff bases enhance antibacterial activity compared to the free ligand, especially with methyl-containing complexes being the most active derivatives. In particular, Zn and Pb methyl complexes exhibited the lowest MIC values. Therefore, methyl complexes were the most active derivatives, with activity comparable to ampicillin, particularly against *P. aeruginosa*. [39] Moreover, literature data for antimicrobial activity for some Pd(II) complexes with N,N donor chelating ligands evaluated on *E. coli* showed the MIC values were comparable to those reported here. [40,41,42] The antimicrobial activity of three palladium(II) complexes containing imidazo[1,2-a]pyridine as a precursor was evaluated against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *B. spizizenii*, *E. coli*, and *P. aeruginosa*. [43] One of the complexes showed MIC and MBC values against *S. aureus* (18.75 and 75.00 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively), similar to those observed in our study. Konakanchi et al. [44] studied the antibacterial activity of Pd, Co, Ni, Cu, and Zn complexes and reported that the Pd complex exhibited broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against *Proteus vulgaris*, *K. pneumoniae*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, and *B. subtilis*. The MIC values for *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* are of the same order of magnitude as those obtained in the present study. Aljohani et al. [45] screened the biological activity of Mn, Pd, Zn, and VO complexes and found that

the Pd complex exhibited the highest antibacterial and antifungal activity compared with the other complexes, with activity comparable to that of the reference drugs. These findings are consistent with the results of the present study. An analysis of the literature suggests that palladium(II) complexes possess significant antimicrobial activity and that the substantial structural diversity of palladium-based compounds influences this activity. Comparative evaluation with standard antibiotics revealed that some complexes showed MIC values comparable to or even lower than streptomycin and chloramphenicol, especially against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. enteritidis*. This suggests that these metal complexes could serve as promising leads for the development of new antimicrobial agents. The antifungal activity against *C. albicans* was limited across both ligands and complexes. The minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBC) and minimum mycoidal concentrations (MMC) presented in this study show differences in antimicrobial activity between the uncoordinated ligands (**L1-L5**) and their corresponding metal complexes (**C1-C5**). Overall, the uncoordinated ligands exhibited minimal to no bactericidal activity, with MBC values consistently exceeding 310 µg/mL for nearly all tested microbial strains. This indicates that the ligands have limited antimicrobial potential in their uncoordinated forms.

Differing from the ligands, the metal complexes exhibited superior antimicrobial activity. Complexes **C1-C4** showed significant activity against a range of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, with MBC values between 10 and 160 µg/mL. Among them, **C2** showed good activity against *S. aureus* (10 µg/mL), *E. faecalis* (40 µg/mL), *E. coli* (80 µg/mL), and *E. aerogenes* (40 µg/mL), as well as moderate antifungal activity against *C. albicans* (MMC = 160 µg/mL). **C1**, **C3**, and **C4** were effective against *S. aureus* and *E. faecalis*. None of the metal complexes showed appreciable activity against *P. aeruginosa* or *S. enteritidis*, which are known to be more resistant due to robust outer membrane structures and active efflux mechanisms [46]. Compared to standard antibiotics, such as streptomycin and chloramphenicol, some metal complexes, particularly **C2**, demonstrated comparable activity against specific strains.

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of selected agents against pathogenic microbial strains from ATCC collection (µg/mL)

Agents (µg/mL)	Microbial strains from ATCC collection							
	<i>S. aureus</i> 25923 MIC/MBC	<i>B. cereus</i> 11778 MIC/MBC	<i>E. faecalis</i> 29212 MIC/MBC	<i>E. coli</i> 25922 MIC/MBC	<i>P. aeruginosa</i> 9027 MIC/MBC	<i>S. enteritidis</i> 13076 MIC/MBC	<i>E. aerogenes</i> 13048 MIC/MBC	<i>C. albicans</i> 10231 MIC/MMC*
L1	>310/>310	310/>310	>310/>310	310/>310	80/>310	80/>310	>310/>310	>310/>310
L2	>310/>310	310/>310	>310/>310	310/>310	10/>310	80/>310	>310/>310	>310/>310
L3	>310/>310	310/>310	>310/>310	310/>310	20/>310	80/>310	>310/>310	>310/>310
L4	>310/>310	20/>310	>310/>310	160/310	10/>310	10/>310	>310/>310	>310/>310
L5	>310/>310	20/>310	>310/>310	80/310	10/>310	10/>310	>310/>310	>310/>310
C1	40/80	20/>310	80/80	10/>310	20/>310	2/>310	160/310	80/160
C2	5/10	10/>310	10/40	2/80	5/>310	1/>310	40/40	160/160
C3	10/160	80/>310	10/160	5/>310	10/>310	1/>310	20/40	160/310
C4	20/40	10/>310	5/80	2/>310	10/>310	1/>310	20/40	160/310
C5	10/>310	20/>310	2/160	2/>310	5/>310	1/>310	80/310	160/310
CP	40/310	80/>310	20/160	80/160	40/>310	40/>310	40/80	160/310
Streptomycin	0.5/0.5	0.5/0.5	16.0/16.0	16.0/16.0	8.0/8.0	4.0/4.0	0.5/0.5	Nystatin*
Chloramphenicol	1.0/8.0	1.0/4.0	16.0/16.0	16.0/16.0	4.0/16.0	4.0/8.0	1.0/1.0	16.0/16.0

*MMC - minimal microbicidal concentration for yeast

4. Conclusions

A series of four novel Schiff bases and five new Pd(II) complexes were synthesized and fully characterized. Among them, four Schiff bases were synthesized from 9-antracenealdehyde and 4-methyl-1,2-phenylenediamine, 4-chloro-1,2-phenylenediamine, 4,5-dimethyl-1,2-phenylenediamine, and methyl 3,4-diaminobenzoate are unknown in the literature. **L1-L5** were bonded to the metal ion bidentately through N,N coordination. All complexes have molar conductivity values from 3-16 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, which confirms a “zero” type complex, e.g., all complexes are neutral.

In addition, antimicrobial evaluation of ligands (**L1-L5**) and their metal complexes (**C1-C5**) showed that metal coordination significantly enhanced activity. While free ligands had limited to moderate activity, mainly against Gram-negative bacteria, such as *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *S. enteritidis*, the complexes showed stronger antimicrobial activity, including efficacy against *C. albicans*.

Complexes **C2** through **C5** showed the most promising bacteriostatic effect, with MIC values in the range (1-10) against multiple resistant strains. In particular, **C2** showed significant activity against all tested bacterial strains, surpassing the standard antibiotics streptomycin and chloramphenicol in several cases. These findings underscore the potential of metal-ligand coordination as a promising strategy to enhance antimicrobial activity. The results presented in this work strongly supports literature data that palladium(II) complexes exhibit significant antibacterial and antifungal activity, comparable with some standard antibiotics such as streptomycin and chloramphenicol. Also, if we look at ligand structure, we can conclude that 9-anthracenyl-based ligands (**L1-L5**) enhance Pd(II) complex antimicrobial activity. The highest activity of **C2** containing methylated ligand, similar to Zn or Pb(II) complexes with methylated aromatic Schiff base ligands described in the literature, the most probably indicates that methyl group also has significant rule in antimicrobial activity.

Author contributions

J.P., S.G.S, T.M.K, and S.N. conceived and designed the experiments. A.K., T.P., M.D., M.T. and J.A. collected the data. A.K., T.P., M.D., M.T., and J.A. carried out the experiments. A.K., T.P., M.D., J.A., and J.P. contributed data and analysis tools. A.K., T.P., J.P., and M.D. took the lead in writing the manuscript. All authors provided critical feedback and helped shape the research, analysis, and manuscript.

Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the Supplementary Information. Supplementary information (SI): NMR spectra (^1H , ^{13}C), IR spectra, and Mass Spectra.

Funding declarations: This work was funded by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development, and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia, under contract numbers 451-03-136/2025-03/200168, 451-03-137/2025-03/200113, and 451-03-136/2025-03/200288. This work was also financially supported by the European Union’s Horizon Europe program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions grant agreement No. 101086373.

Ethics declarations

Conflict of interest: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Ethical approval and consent to participate: Not applicable.

Consent for publication: Not applicable.

Literature

- ¹ C.L.J. Murray et.al. *The Lancet* **399**, 629 (2019). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(21\)02724-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02724-0)
- ² M.E.A. de Kraker, A.J. Stewardson, S. Harbarth. *PLoS Med.* **13**, 1 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002184>
- ³ R.J. Fair, Y. Tor. *Persp. Med. Chem.* **6**, 25 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.4137/PMc.s14459>
- ⁴ M.I. Hutchings, A.W. Truman, B. Wilkinson. *Curr. Opin. Microb.* **51**, 72 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mib.2019.10.008>
- ⁵ D.G.J. Larsson, C.F. Flach. *Nature Rev. Microb.* **20**, 257 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41579-021-00649-x>
- ⁶ V. Vitali, S. Zineddu, L. Messori *RSC Adv.* **15**, 748 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4ra07449a>
- ⁷ A. Frei, J. Zuegg, A.G. Elliott, M. Baker, S. Braese, C. Brown, F. Chen, C.G. Dowson, G. Dujardin, N. Jung, A.P. King, A.M. Mansour, M. Massi, J. Moat, H.A. Mohamed, A.K. Renfrew, P.J. Rutledge, P.J. Sadler, M.H. Todd, C.E. Willans, J.J. Wilsom, M.A. Cooper, A.T. Blaskovich. *Chem. Sci.* **11**, 2627 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9SC06460E>
- ⁸ O. Zalevskaia, Y. Gur'eva, A. Kutchin. *Russ. Chem. Rev.* **92**, RCR5093 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.59761/RCR5093>
- ⁹ M. Rizzotto, In: Bobbarala V. (ed) Metal Complexes as Antimicrobial Agents, *Intechopen*. (2012) <https://doi.org/10.5772/1085>
- ¹⁰ A. Garoufis, S.K. Hadjidakou, N. Hadjiliadis. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **253**, 1384 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccr.2008.09.011>
- ¹¹ P.G. Mahajan, N.C. Dige, S.B. Suryawanshi, D.K. Dalavi, A.A. Kamble, D.P. Bhopate, A.N. Kadam, V.V. Kondalkar, G.B. Kolekar, S.R. Patil. *J. Fluoresc.* **28**, 207 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10895-017-2183-2>
- ¹² P.G. Mahajan, N.C. Dige, N.K. Desai, S.R. Patil, V.V. Kondalkar, S.K. Hong, K.H. Lee. *Spectrochim. Acta A: Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.* **198**, 136 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2018.03.004>
- ¹³ M.N. Uddin, S.S. Ahmed, S.M.R. Alam. *J. Coord. Chem.* **73**, 3109 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958972.2020.1854745>
- ¹⁴ G. Shen, J. Li. *J. App. Polym. Sci.* **78**, 676 (2000). [https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628\(20001017\)78:3<676::AID-APP240>3.0.CO;2-E](https://doi.org/10.1002/1097-4628(20001017)78:3<676::AID-APP240>3.0.CO;2-E)
- ¹⁵ S. Thakur, A. Jaryal, A. Bhalla. *Results Chem.* **7**, 101350 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2024.101350>
- ¹⁶ W. Qin, S. Long, M. Panunzio, S. Biondi. *Molecules* **18**, 12264 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules181012264>
- ¹⁷ E. Raczuk, B. Dmochowska, J. Samaszko-Fiertek, J. Madaj. *Molecules* **27**, 787 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27030787>
- ¹⁸ L. Otero, M. Vieites, L. Boiani, A. Denicola, C. Rigol, L. Opazo, C. Olea-Azar, J. Maya, A. Morello, R. Krauth-Siegel, O. Piro, E. Castellano, M. González, D. Gambino, H. Cerecetto. *J. Med. Chem.* **49**, 3322 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm0512241>
- ¹⁹ D.Y. Ma, L.X. Zhang, X.Y. Rao, T.L. Wu, D.H. Li, X.Q. Xie. *J. Coord. Chem.* **66**, 1486 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1080/00958972.2013.783699>
- ²⁰ M. Sönmez, H.G. Sogukomerogullari, F. Öztemel, İ. Berber. *Med. Chem. Res.* **23**, 3451 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00044-014-0925-0>
- ²¹ A. Abu-Surrah, K. Safieh, I. Ahmad, M. Abdalla, M. Ayoub, A. Qaroush, A. Abu-Mahtheieh. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **45**, 471 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2009.10.029>
- ²² A. Karaküçük-İyidoğan, D. Taşdemir, E. Oruç-Emre, J. Balzarini. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* **46**, 5616 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2011.09.031>

- ²³ S.B. Deepthi, P. Ramesh, R. Trivedi, S.K. Buddana, R.S. Prakasham. *Inorg. Chim. Acta.* **435**, 200 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2015.06.027>
- ²⁴ C. Rĩmbu, R. Danac, A. Pui. *Chem. Pharm. Bull.* **62**, 12 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1248/cpb.c12-01087>
- ²⁵ C.E. Satheesh, P. Raghavendra Kumar, P. Sharma, K. Lingaraju, B.S. Palakshamurthy, H. Raja Naika. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **442**, 1 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2015.11.017>
- ²⁶ A.N. Rosniza, M.A. Hamali, A.M. Low, E.H. Anouar, H.M. Youssef, H. Bahron, A.M. Tajuddin. *J. Mol. Struct.* **1260**, 132821 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2022.132821>
- ²⁷ E.A. Nyawade, M.O. Onani, S. Meyer, P. Dube. *Chem. Pap.* **74**, 3705 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11696-019-00986-5>
- ²⁸ K. Meena, P.K. Baroliya. *Chem. Biodivers.* **20**, e202300158 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbdv.202300158>
- ²⁹ L.O. Amaral, L.R. Santiago, W.V. Ferreira, J.D.S. Silva, A.J. Bortoluzzi, M.B. Marques, M.J.F. Costa, P.H. Sette-de-Souza, S.M. Soares. *J. Mol. Struct.* **1328**, 141403 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2025.141403>
- ³⁰ K. Andiappan, A. Sanmugam, E. Deivanayagam, K. Karuppasamy, H-S Kim, D. Vikraman. *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* **124**, 403 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2018.11.251>
- ³¹ G. Navale, S. Singh, S. Agrawal, C. Ghosh, A. Roy Choudhury, P. Roy, D. Sarkar, K. Ghosh. *Dalton Trans.* **51**, 16371 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2DT02577A>
- ³² F. Basolo, J.L. Burmeister, On Being Well-coordinated: A Half-century of Research on Transition Metal Complexes: Selected Papers of Fred Basolo. World Scientific. (2003) p. 272. ISBN 978-981-238-087-6
- ³³ A. Mounica, C. Balachandran, D. Gopalakrishnan, P. Sivasakthi, M. Prakash, S. Aoki, M. Ganeshpandian. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **530**, 120701 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2021.120701>
- ³⁴ CLSI. Methods for Dilution Antimicrobial Susceptibility Tests for Bacteria that Grows Aerobically. Approved Standard, 9th Edition, CLSI Document M07- A9, Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute, Wayne, PA, USA (2012).
- ³⁵ N. Radulovic, M. Dekic, Z. Stojanovic-Radic, S. Zoranic. *Chem. Biodivers.* **7**, 2783e2800 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867311320070008>
- ³⁶ W.J. Geary. *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **7**, 81 (1971). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-8545\(00\)80009-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-8545(00)80009-0)
- ³⁷ C. Nwobodo, D. Malachy Chigozie Ugwu, C. Oliseloke Anie, M.T.S. Al-Ouqaili, J. Chinedu Ikem, U.V. Chigozie, M. Morteza Saki. *J. Clin. Lab. Anal.* **36(9)** 1 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcla.24655>
- ³⁸ H. Abdulbari, S. Ünlü, F.T. Elmalı. *J. Mol. Struct.* **1293**, 136156 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2023.136156>
- ³⁹ M. Sahin, N. Kocak, D. Erdenay, U. Arslan. *Spectrochim. Acta A* **103**, 400 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2012.11.006>
- ⁴⁰ S.S. Jovičić Milić, V.V. Jevtić, D.Lj. Stojković, D.S. Petrović, E.H. Avdović, Z.S. Marković, I.D. Radojević, L. Čomić, V.S. Mladenović. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **510**, 119743 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2020.119743>
- ⁴¹ D.S. Petrović, S.S. Jovicić Milić, M.B. Đukić, I.D. Radojević, R.M. Jelić, M.M. Jurišević, G.P. Radić, N.M. Gajović, N.N. Arsenijević, I.P. Jovanović, N.V. Marković, D.Lj. Stojković, V.V. Jevtić. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **528**, 120601 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2021.120601>
- ⁴² B.B. Zmejkovski, N.D. Pantelić, G.N. Kaluđerović. *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **534**, 120797 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ica.2022.120797>
- ⁴³ Md.N. Alam, J.Q. Yu, P. Beale, P. Turner, N. Proschogo, F. Huq. *ChemistrySelect* **5**, 668 (2020). <https://dx.doi.org/10.1002/slct.201902438>
- ⁴⁴ R. Konakanchi, G.S. Pamidimalla, J. Prashanth, T. Naveen, L.R. Kotha. *BioMetals* **34**, 529 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10534-021-00293-1>
- ⁴⁵ E.T. Aljohani, M.R. Shehata, F. Alkhatib, S.O. Alzahrani, A.M. Abu-Dief. *Appl. Organomet. Chem.* **35**, 6154 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1002/aoc.6154>
- ⁴⁶ P. Zheng, R. Raudonis, B.R. Glick, T.J. Lin, Z. Cheng. *Biotechnol. Adv.* **37(1)** 177 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2018.11.013>